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WEAKLY C -CONTRACTIVE MAPPINGS IN CONE METRIC SPACES

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Abstract. In this article, we introduce the class of weakly c -contractive mappings in cone metric spaces. A fixed point theorem is established in the framework of cone metric spaces.

Keywords: cone metric space; C -contractive mappings; fixed point.

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1. Introduction

Recently, Huang and Zhang introduced the concept of cone metric spaces by replacing the set of real numbers with an ordered Banach space, for more details; see [4] and the references therein. Subsequently, many fixed point results concerning self mappings in such spaces have been investigated; see [2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10] and the references therein. In this article, we extend some results in [1] to the framework of cone metric spaces. In this paper, the cones are strongly minihedral and normal to endow the cone metric spaces with an appropriate topology; see [11].

The aim of this paper is to investigate fixed point problems of C -contractive mappings. A fixed point theorem is established in the framework of cone metric spaces.

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The organization of this paper is as follows. In Section 2, we provide some necessary preliminaries. In Section 3, a fixed point theorem is established in the framework of cone metric spaces. The result presented in this paper mainly generalizes the result of Binayak [1].

2. Preliminaries

We first recall some known definitions, notations and results concerning cones in Banach spaces.

Definition 2.1. Let E be a real Banach space with norm $\|\cdot\|$ and let P be a subset of E . Then P is called a cone if and only if

- (1) P is closed, nonempty and $P \neq \{\theta\}$, where θ is the zero vector in E ;
- (2) for any $a, b \geq 0$ (nonnegative real numbers), and $x, y \in P$, we have

$$ax + by \in P;$$
- (3) for $x \in P$, if $-x \in P$, then $x = \theta$.

Given a cone P in a Banach space E , we define on E a partial order \preceq with respect to P by

$$x \preceq y \iff y - x \in P.$$

We also write $x \prec y$ whenever $x \preceq y$ and $x \neq y$, while $x \ll y$ will stand for $y - x \in \text{Int}(P)$, where $\text{Int}(P)$ stand for the interior of P .

The cone P is called normal if there is a real number $K > 0$, such that for all $x, y \in E$, we have

$$\theta \preceq x \preceq y \implies \|x\| \leq K\|y\|.$$

The least positive number satisfying this inequality is called the normal constant of P . Therefore, we shall say that P is a K -normal cone to indicate the fact that the normal constant is K .

The cone is said to be regular if every increasing sequence which is bounded from above is convergent. That is, if (x_n) is a sequence such that $x_n \preceq x_2 \preceq \cdots \preceq y$ for some $y \in E$, then there exists $x^* \in E$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\| = 0$.

Lemma 2.1. [13, 15] *Every regular cone is normal. The cone P is regular if every decreasing sequence which is bounded from below is convergent.*

Definition 2.2. *Let X be a non empty set. A function $d : X \times X \rightarrow E$ is called a cone metric on X if:*

- (d1) $\theta \preceq d(x, y) \quad \forall x \in X$ and $d(x, y) = \theta$ if and only if $x = y$;
- (d2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x) \quad \forall x, y \in X$;
- (d3) $d(x, z) \preceq d(x, y) + d(y, z) \quad \forall x, y, z \in X$.

The pair (X, d) is called a cone metric space.

From the definition of the order given by a cone P , it is obvious that $x \in P \iff \theta \preceq x$. Hence, we can define a concept of positivity on a Banach space as follow.

Definition 2.3. *Let E be a real Banach space. Let P be a cone on E and \preceq the partial order with respect to P . An element $x \in E$ is said to be a nonnegative vector if $\theta \preceq x$ and positive vector if $\theta \prec x$. Hence P is the set of all nonnegative elements. We shall use the following notations:*

- $[\theta, \longrightarrow [:= P = \{x \in E : \theta \preceq x\}$;
- $] \theta, \longrightarrow [:= \{x \in E : \theta \prec x\}$.

Definition 2.4. *A subset A of E is said to be bounded from above with respect to P (or upper bounded) if there exists $x_0 \in E$ such that $a \preceq x_0$ for all $a \in A$. A subset A of E is said to be bounded from below with respect to P (or lower bounded) if there exists $x_0 \in E$ such that $x_0 \preceq a$ for all $a \in A$.*

Definition 2.5. *A cone P is said to be minihedral if $x \vee y := \sup\{x, y\}$ exists for all $x, y \in E$ and strongly minihedral if every subset of E which is bounded from above has a supremum.*

We also recall the following lemma, which we take from [11] and give the proof as it is there.

Lemma 2.6. *Let (X, d) be a quasi-cone metric space. Then for each $c \in E$, $c \gg \theta$, there exists $\sigma > 0$ such that $x \ll c$ whenever $\|x\| < \sigma$, $x \in E$.*

Proof. Since $c \gg \theta$, we have $c \in \text{Int}(P)$. Hence, we find $\sigma > 0$ such that $\{x \in E : \|x - c\| < \sigma\} \subset \text{Int}(P)$. If $\|x\| < \sigma$, then $\|(c - x) - c\| = \|-x\| = \|x\| < \sigma$ and hence $(c - x) \in \text{Int}(P)$.

Lemma 2.7. *Let (X, d) be a cone metric space over a cone K -normal cone P . Then one has*

- a) $Int(P) + Int(P) \subset Int(P)$ and $\lambda Int(P) \subset Int(P)$ for any positive real number λ .
- b) For any given $c \gg \theta$ and $c_0 \gg \theta$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\frac{c_0}{n_0} \ll c$.
- c) If (a_n) and (b_n) are sequences in E such that $a_n \rightarrow a$, $b_n \rightarrow b$ and $a_n \preceq b_n$ for all $n \geq 1$, then $a \preceq b$.

Proposition 2.8. Let (X, q) be a cone metric space over a cone P . If $a \preceq \lambda a$, where $0 \leq \lambda < 1$, then $a = \theta$.

Definition 2.9. Let (x_n) be a sequence in a cone metric space (X, d) .

- (a) (x_n) is convergent to $x \in X$ and we denote $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$, if for every $c \in E$ with $c \gg \theta$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall n, m \geq n_0 \quad d(x_n, x) \ll c;$$

- (b) (x_n) is called Cauchy if for every $c \in E$ with $c \gg \theta$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\forall n, m \geq n_0 \quad d(x_n, x_m) \ll c.$$

Definition 2.10. A cone metric space (X, d) is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence in X is convergent in X .

Lemma 2.11. [4] Let (X, d) be a cone metric space over a cone K -normal cone P . The sequence (x_n) converges to $x \in X$ if and only if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x) = \theta$. The sequence (x_n) is Cauchy if and only if $\lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_m) = \theta$.

Throughout this paper, we shall assume that the cones are strongly minihedral and K -normal, hence regular. Except otherwise stated, the notation \preceq designates the partial order with respect to P . Furthermore, we shall assume that $Int(P) \neq \emptyset$.

We conclude this section by the following proposition.

Proposition 2.12. [11] Every cone metric space (X, d) is a topological space.

3. Main results

In [1], Binayak proved the following result.

Theorem B. *Let $T : X \rightarrow X$, where (X, d) is a complete metric space, be a weak C-contraction. Then T has a fixed point.*

We generalize this result in the setting of cone metric spaces in this section.

Definition 3.1. *A mapping $T : X \rightarrow X$, where (X, d) is a complete cone metric space, is said to be a weakly C-contractive or a weak C-contraction if for all $x, y \in X$,*

$$(0.1) \quad d(Tx, Ty) \preceq \frac{1}{2} [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] - \psi(d(x, Ty), d(y, Tx)),$$

where $\psi : P \times P \rightarrow P$ is a continuous mapping such that $\psi(x, y) = \theta$ if and only if $x = y = \theta$.

Lemma 3.1. *Let (X, d) be a cone metric space over a K -normal cone P . Then for any $c \in P$ and any $a \in E$, $a - c \preceq a$.*

Proof. Indeed, we have

$$\theta \preceq c \iff c \in P \iff a - (a - c) \in P \iff a - c \preceq a.$$

Theorem 3.3. *Let $T : X \rightarrow X$, where (X, d) is a complete cone metric space, be a weak C-contraction. Then T has a fixed point.*

Proof. Let (x_n) be a sequence generated in the iteration $x_{n+1} = Tx_n$. If $x_n = x_{n+1} = Tx_n$, then x_n is a fixed point of T . Next, we assume $x_n \neq x_{n+1}$. Using (0.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\ &\preceq \frac{1}{2} [d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) + d(x_n, Tx_{n-1})] - \psi(d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n), d(x_n, Tx_{n-1})) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) - \psi(d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}), \theta) \\ (0.2) \quad &\preceq \frac{1}{2} (d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})) - \psi(d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}), \theta). \end{aligned}$$

Using (0.2), we find from Lemma 3.1 that

$$(0.3) \quad d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \preceq d(x_{n-1}, x_n).$$

Thus $(d(x_n, x_{n+1}))$ is a monotone decreasing sequence in E . Moreover, this sequence is bounded below by θ and since P is regular, the sequence $(d(x_n, x_{n+1}))$ is convergent. Let $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow r$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Next we prove that $r = \theta$.

$$\begin{aligned}
d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\
&\preceq \frac{1}{2}(d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) + d(x_n, Tx_{n-1})) - \psi(d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}), d(x_n, x_n)) \\
&\preceq \frac{1}{2}d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) \\
&\preceq \frac{1}{2}(d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})).
\end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, we see that

$$r \preceq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2}d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) \preceq \frac{1}{2}r + \frac{1}{2}r,$$

or

$$(0.4) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) = 2r.$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (0.2) and using (0.4) and the continuity of ψ , we have

$$r \preceq r - \psi(2r, \theta)$$

or

$$-\psi(2r, \theta) \in P,$$

which is a contradiction unless $r = \theta$. Thus we have established that

$$(0.5) \quad d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow \theta \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Next we show that (x_n) is a Cauchy sequence. If otherwise, then there exists $\varepsilon \gg \theta$ and increasing sequences of integers $(m(k))$ and $(n(k))$ such that for all integers k , $n(k) > m(k)$, $d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) \succeq \varepsilon$ and $d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) \ll \varepsilon$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
\varepsilon &\preceq d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) \\
&= d(Tx_{m(k)-1}, Tx_{n(k)-1}) \\
&\preceq \frac{1}{2}(d(x_{m(k)-1}, Tx_{n(k)-1}) + d(x_{n(k)-1}, Tx_{m(k)-1})) \\
&\quad - \psi(d(x_{m(k)-1}, Tx_{n(k)-1}), d(x_{n(k)-1}, Tx_{m(k)-1})) \text{ by (0.1)} \\
(0.6) \quad &= \frac{1}{2}(d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) + d(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{m(k)})) - \psi(d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}), d(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{m(k)})).
\end{aligned}$$

Again, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon &\preceq d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) \\ &\preceq d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) + d(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) \\ &\preceq \varepsilon + d(x_{n(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}).\end{aligned}$$

Letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (0.5), we obtain

$$(0.7) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}) = \varepsilon$$

and

$$(0.8) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) = \varepsilon.$$

Indeed, we also have

$$\begin{aligned}d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}) &\preceq d(x_{m(k)}, x_{m(k)-1}) \\ &\quad + d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) \\ &\quad + d(x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)-1}).\end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) \preceq d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{m(k)}) + d(x_{m(k)}, x_{n(k)}).$$

Letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above two inequalities and using (0.5), (0.7) and (0.8) we get

$$(0.9) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{m(k)-1}, x_{n(k)}) = \varepsilon.$$

Next, letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ in (0.6) and using (0.5), (0.8) and (0.9) we obtain

$$\varepsilon \preceq \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon + \varepsilon) - \psi(\varepsilon, \varepsilon).$$

Or $\psi(\varepsilon, \varepsilon) \preceq \theta$, which is a contradiction since $\varepsilon \gg \theta$. Hence (x_n) is a Cauchy sequence and therefore is convergent in the complete cone metric space (X, d) . Let $x_n \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. We

prove that z is a fixed point for T . Indeed, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(z, Tz) &\preceq d(z, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, Tz) \\
 &\preceq d(z, x_{n+1}) + d(Tx_n, Tz) \\
 &\preceq d(z, x_{n+1}) + \frac{1}{2}(d(z, Tx_n)) - \psi(d(z, x_n), d(x_n, Tz)) \\
 &= d(z, x_{n+1}) + \frac{1}{2}(d(z, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, Tz)) - \psi(d(z, x_{n+1}), d(x_n, Tz)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, using the continuity of ψ , we obtain

$$d(z, Tz) \preceq \frac{1}{2}d(z, Tz) - \psi(\theta, d(z, Tz)) \preceq \frac{1}{2}d(z, Tz),$$

which is a contradiction unless $d(z, Tz) = \theta$. Hence $z = Tz$.

Next we establish that the fixed point z is unique. If z_1 and z_2 are two fixed points of T , then

$$d(z_1, z_2) = d(Tz_1, Tz_2) \preceq \frac{1}{2}(d(z_1, Tz_2) + d(z_2, Tz_1)) - \psi(d(z_1, Tz_2), d(z_2, Tz_1)).$$

That is,

$$d(z_1, z_2) \preceq d(z_1, z_2) - \psi(d(z_1, z_2), d(z_1, z_2)) \prec d(z_1, z_2),$$

which by property of ψ is a contradiction unless $d(z_1, z_2) = \theta$, that is, $z_1 = z_2$. This completes the proof.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests.

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